

Increasing the Fairness of Photovoltaic Curtailments for Voltage Management in Distribution Grids

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Abstract—The increasing penetration of photovoltaic systems (PV) in distribution grids can create significant over-voltage conditions due to intense reverse power flow. In addition to reactive power control, PV curtailments are often employed for voltage regulation to ensure compliance with the regulatory limits. However, reducing the output power of a PV system results to a revenue drop for the owners, raising concerns about fairness. Relevant works often address this issue through penalty terms in the objective function, but most works neglect the trade-off between fairness and total curtailments, i.e., increasing fairness leads to an increase of total curtailments. This paper proposes a novel methodology to enhance the fairness of PV curtailments for voltage regulation while ensuring that the increase in total curtailments is within a specified acceptable limit. In this direction, the Jain’s fairness index is used to quantitatively measure fairness, which is incorporated in the optimization process as a second order cone program constraint. An iterative algorithm based on the bisection method is then developed to increase fairness until the allowable total curtailments are reached. Simulation results demonstrate the capability of the proposed method to improve the fairness of PV curtailments, considering different levels of allowable total curtailments.

Index Terms—Curtailments, fairness, low voltage distribution grid, photovoltaic, voltage control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental concerns and soaring electricity prices have led to a strong growth of rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems in low voltage distribution grids (LVDG) over the past years, which is expected to continue for the foreseeable future [1]. However, besides their beneficial effects, the increasing penetration of scattered PV systems presents several challenges in the operation of the distribution grid [2], [3]. Specifically, the low local demand from the consumers during peak PV generation leads to an intense reverse power flow, which can create significant over-voltage issues. Therefore, to maintain network integrity under high penetration of PVs, these over-voltage conditions must be prevented.

In this direction, network reinforcements and wired solutions, such as a distribution line upgrade, on-load tap-change transformers, and static var compensators can be utilized for

voltage management [4], [5], with however very high costs. Alternatively, PV inverters can aid in the voltage regulation by providing reactive power. In fact, in most countries the voltage regulation by PVs through reactive power provision is a requirement that is specified in the national grid codes. Typically, local droop-based schemes are required such as the power factor/Watt or Var/Volt modes [6]. More sophisticated approaches can be found in the literature [7], [8] where their aim is to minimize the overall deployment of reactive power. However, in LVDGs, the distribution lines have high resistance to reactance R/X ratio, therefore reducing the effectiveness of reactive power [9]. Consequently, high amounts of reactive power are needed for adequate voltage regulation, which increases network utilization and grid losses, and requires oversized inverters.

Due to the high R/X ratio in LVDGs, active power control is an effective method for voltage management. For addressing over-voltage conditions, either PV curtailments or energy storage systems can be utilized. The latter however is still not widely available in LVDGs due to the considerable investment needed by the end-users. For PV curtailments, most methods aim to minimize the curtailed energy needed to ensure voltage limits by using the sensitivity of the grid’s voltage to the PVs’ active power injection $\Delta V/\Delta P$ [10], [11]. However, due to the radial configuration of LVDGs, such schemes tend to over-penalize the PVs near the end-of-feeder (EoF). This location-based penalty can create large revenue disparity among the PV owners, raising the issue of fair PV curtailment.

For this reason, fairness-aware methods for PV curtailment based on optimization schemes have been proposed recently in the literature. In [12], the PV curtailment fairness is evaluated using three different objective functions based on the equity of financial benefits, energy exports, and relative curtailments. To force more fair PV curtailments, an additional penalty term is introduced in the objective function in [13]. Similarly, a fairness cost function is utilized in [14] where three different interpretations of PV curtailment fairness are examined. A distributed method is presented in [15] with the aim to ensure proportionally equal curtailments, in relation to the available PV exports, by introducing a penalty term on the objective function as well as additional constraints.

In general, most fairness-aware methods increase the fairness of PV curtailments by introducing additional penalty

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terms to the objective function of an optimization problem. However, increasing fairness comes at a cost of higher total curtailments. While some works acknowledge this trade-off, most of them do not explicitly consider it in their formulation. In addition, increasing the fairness through penalty terms does not offer controllability over this trade-off, such as specifying a minimum fairness value or a maximum acceptable increase in total curtailments.

In this direction, the contribution of this paper is the development of a novel methodology to maximize the fairness of PV curtailments while ensuring the increase of total curtailments is within an acceptable limit. The fairness of PV curtailments is quantified in this paper using the Jain's fairness index [16], which is incorporated in the optimization process as a second-order cone program (SOCP) constraint. To ensure that the increment of total curtailments is within an acceptable value, an iterative process based on the bisection method is developed that increases the fairness index until the total curtailments reach their specified limit.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II the proposed methodology is presented with simulation results shown in Section III. Conclusions are given in Section IV.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The objective of the proposed Curtailment-Fairness Coordination (CFC) scheme is to maximize the fairness of PV curtailments while ensuring that the increase of total curtailments is within a pre-specified acceptable limit. In this direction, first the minimum total PV curtailments needed to mitigate over-voltage conditions are determined by problem \mathbb{P}^L .

A. Minimum PV Curtailments for Voltage Regulation

1) *Objective Function:* The objective function of problem \mathbb{P}^L is defined as the summation of the individual curtailment of each PV system, given by

$$f_C(\mathbf{P}^L) = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} P_{g,m}^C, \quad (1)$$

where sets \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{M}_g , $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$ denote the nodes and phases, respectively, that contain the PV systems. Variables $P_{g,m}^C$ denote the curtailment of the PV system located in node g and connected to phase m , while \mathbf{P}^L denotes the vector-form of $P_{g,m}^C$ in problem \mathbb{P}^L for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$.

2) *Constraints:* The curtailment power $P_{g,m}^C$ of each PV system is limited by its available generation, as given by

$$P_{g,m}^C \leq P_{g,m}^G, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, m \in \mathcal{M}_g, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{g,m}^G$ denotes the maximum available generating power of the PV system located in node g , phase m . Furthermore, the voltage at each node of the LVDG must be within the admissible limits, as defined by

$$V_{k,p} \leq \bar{V}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, p \in \mathcal{P}_k, \quad (3)$$

where set $k \in \mathcal{K}$ represents the system nodes and $\mathcal{P} = [a, b, c]$ denotes the system phases with $\mathcal{P}_k \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ defined as the

available phases at node k . Constant \bar{V} denotes the upper voltage limit, as defined by the national grid codes. A convex and computationally efficient optimization problem is obtained by using a linearized grid model where the grid voltage is related to the active power through sensitivity coefficients [11], [12] for all $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_k$, as given by

$$V_{k,p} = \hat{V}_{k,p} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} q_{k,g}^{p,m} (P_{g,m}^C - \tilde{P}_{g,m}^C), \quad (4)$$

where constant $q_{k,g}^{p,m}$ (V/kW) denotes the sensitivity of the grid voltage at node k phase p in relation to the active power at node g phase m . Furthermore, $\hat{V}_{k,p}$ denotes the voltage measurement before the curtailment set points $P_{g,m}^C$ are applied, and $\tilde{P}_{g,m}^C$ denotes the PV curtailment set point from the previous control cycle. Therefore, in case of over-voltage conditions ($\hat{V}_{k,p} > \bar{V}$), new curtailment set points $P_{g,m}^C$ are calculated to ensure compliance with the regulatory limits. Note that the sensitivity coefficients $q_{k,g}^{p,m}$ can be calculated either by inverting the Jacobian matrix, by a perturb-and-observe approach, or by the use of the linearized power flow equations for radial distribution grids [17].

The optimization problem \mathbb{P}^L that minimizes the total PV curtailments needed for voltage regulation is summarized as

$$\mathbb{P}^L : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (1) \\ \text{subject to} & (2) - (4). \end{cases}$$

B. Problem Statement

The proposed CFC scheme, defined by problem \mathbb{P}^E , maximizes the fairness of PV curtailments for voltage regulation, while ensuring a controlled increase in total curtailments.

1) *Objective Function:* In this paper, fairness is quantitatively measured using Jain's index [16]. Therefore, the objective function of problem \mathbb{P}^E is given by

$$-f_J(\mathbf{P}^E) = -\frac{\left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} P_{g,m}^C / \bar{P}_{g,m}\right)^2}{N \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} (P_{g,m}^C / \bar{P}_{g,m})^2}, \quad (5)$$

where constants N and $\bar{P}_{g,m}$ denote the total number and the installed capacity of each PV system, respectively. Furthermore, \mathbf{P}^E denotes the vector-form of $P_{g,m}^C$ in problem \mathbb{P}^E for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $m \in \mathcal{M}_g$. Function $f_J(\mathbf{P}^E)$ takes values in the range $[1/N, 1]$, where $f_J(\mathbf{P}^E) = 1/N$ is the worst case (in terms of fairness) where power is curtailed from only one PV system, while $f_J(\mathbf{P}^E) = 1$ is the best case where all PVs are equally curtailed.

2) *Constraints:* Besides the constraints that limit the curtailment power (2), ensure the mitigation of over-voltage conditions (3), and the linearized grid model (4), the below constraint is added to problem \mathbb{P}^E

$$f_C(\mathbf{P}^E) \leq (1 + \alpha) f_C(\mathbf{P}^L), \quad (6)$$

where input parameter $\alpha \geq 0$ specifies the allowable increase in total curtailments, $f_C(\mathbf{P}^L)$ are the minimum total curtailments obtained from problem \mathbb{P}^L , and $f_C(\mathbf{P}^E)$ are the total curtailments obtained from problem \mathbb{P}^E . Therefore, constraint

(6) ensures that the curtailment fairness is maximized given a controllable increase on the total curtailments by $af_C(\mathbf{P}^L)$.

In summary, problem \mathbb{P}^E is defined as

$$\mathbb{P}^E : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (5) \\ \text{subject to} & (2) - (4), (6). \end{cases}$$

Problem \mathbb{P}^E is non-linear and non-convex which is challenging to solve due to the objective function (5). To obtain a computationally efficient formulation, a novel solution methodology to transform \mathbb{P}^E into a convex SOCP model is presented next.

C. Solution Methodology

1) *Jain's Fairness as a SOCP Constraint:* The non-linear and non-convex objective function of the Jain's fairness index (5) is reformulated to a SOCP constraint, as given by

$$\frac{\left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} P_{g,m}^C / \bar{P}_{g,m}\right)^2}{N \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} (P_{g,m}^C / \bar{P}_{g,m})^2} \geq J_0, \quad (7)$$

where constant J_0 denotes a minimum value of the PV curtailment fairness. The Jain's fairness SOCP constraint (7) can be equivalently expressed as

$$A = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} P_{g,m}^C / \bar{P}_{g,m}, \quad (8a)$$

$$A^2 \geq J_0 N \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} (P_{g,m}^C / \bar{P}_{g,m})^2, \quad (8b)$$

where A is an auxiliary variable.

2) *Iterative Solution:* The reformulation of the Jain's fairness index into the linear (8a) and SOCP (8b) constraints enables control of the PV curtailment fairness, ensuring it satisfies a minimum value set by the input parameter J_0 . Furthermore, the objective function is modified to (1) to achieve the desired fairness value with minimal total curtailments. The proposed relaxed problem \mathbb{P}^R is summarized as

$$\mathbb{P}^R : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (1) \\ \text{subject to} & (2) - (4), (8). \end{cases}$$

Note that the exactness of constraint (8b), i.e., $f_J(\mathbf{P}^R) = J_0$, is ensured by minimizing the objective function (1) in problem \mathbb{P}^R as increasing fairness also increases the total curtailments.

To maximize the PV curtailment fairness while ensuring that the increase in total curtailments is within the specified limit α , an iterative algorithm based on the bisection method is developed. Algorithm 1 summarizes the proposed CFC scheme where problems \mathbb{P}^L and \mathbb{P}^R are both utilized. First, the lower J_{lb} and upper J_{ub} bounds of J_0 are initialized (Line 2) before solving problem \mathbb{P}^L (Line 3) to obtain the minimum PV curtailments needed to prevent over-voltage conditions. The iterative process of the proposed CFC scheme is described in Lines 4-12. Problem \mathbb{P}^R is solved at Line 6 to obtain solution x_{J_0} for the fairness parameter J_0 , as calculated at Line 5. The resulting total PV curtailments $f_C(\mathbf{P}^R)$ are compared with the allowable increase from the solution of problem \mathbb{P}^L at Line 7, given the input parameter α . If the total curtailments of

Algorithm 1 : CFC

- 1: **Input:** e, α .
- 2: **Init.** $J_{lb} = 1/N, J_{ub} = 1$.
- 3: Solve \mathbb{P}^L to obtain $f_C(\mathbf{P}^L)$.
- 4: **while** $J_{ub} - J_{lb} \geq e$ **do**
- 5: Set $J_0 = (J_{ub} + J_{lb}) / 2$.
- 6: Solve \mathbb{P}^R to obtain $x_{J_0}, f_C(\mathbf{P}^R)$.
- 7: **if** $f_C(\mathbf{P}^R) \leq (1 + \alpha)f_C(\mathbf{P}^L)$ **then**
- 8: Set $J_{lb} = J_0, \hat{x} = x_{J_0}, J^M = J_0$.
- 9: **else**
- 10: Set $J_{ub} = J_0$.
- 11: **Return** \hat{x}, J^M .

Notes:

Lines/Cables:	Loads:
— 4x100mm ²	● Phase - A
— 4x50mm ²	● Phase - B
— [4,2]x22mm ²	● Phase - C
— [4,2]x16mm ²	● 3 - Phase
— XLPE	
— 185/90mm ²	

Fig. 1. Considered sub-urban LVDC from the Cyprus power system

problem \mathbb{P}^R are below the specified limit, then the fairness parameter J_0 is increased in the next iteration by setting $J_{lb} = J_0$ in Line 8. Otherwise, set $J_{ub} = J_0$ in Line 10 to decrease the fairness parameter in the next iteration, which will also reduce the total PV curtailments. Convergence is achieved when $J_{ub} - J_{lb}$ becomes smaller than the bisection tolerance e (Line 4). Algorithm 1 returns the solution \hat{x} obtained for the maximum fairness value J^M (Line 11) which results in total curtailments that are within the specified limit. Furthermore, since Algorithm 1 halves the searching space in each iteration, it converges to J^M in $\log_2((1 - J_0)/e)$ iterations.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The operation of the proposed CFC scheme is validated using the LVDC illustrated in Fig. 1, which is a real sub-urban grid from the Cyprus power system. Its complete documentation can be found in the provided link¹. Furthermore, it is assumed that there are 35 PV systems installed at random load nodes with their exact location given in Table I. The install PV capacity is 3 kW for single-phase and 5 kW for three-phase systems with inverters of similar capacities. The load profiles of each consumer are generated using the CREST demand model [18]. The digital twin of the considered network

¹<https://www.kios.ucy.ac.cy/LVtestsystems>

TABLE I
LOCATION OF PV SYSTEMS

Asset	Installed at Nodes
PV	4,6,7,8,11,12,13,15,17,21,26,27,28,31,32,35,38,40, 42,45,47,48,51,56,57,59,60,64,65,67,68,69,71,72,74

Fig. 2. Total PV curtailments in relation with Jain's fairness Index

as well as the CFC scheme are implemented in MATLAB-Simulink. The simulation time is 8 h, from 10 am to 6 pm. All optimization problems are solved using the optimization solver Gurobi [19] on a personal computer with 12 GB RAM and an Intel Core-i7 3.2 GHz processor.

A. Trade-off Between Fairness and Total PV Curtailments

In Fig. 2 the trade-off between fairness and total PV curtailments needed to mitigate over-voltage conditions is illustrated for a single operating point. The lower left point of this figure corresponds to the solution of problem \mathbb{P}^L which yields the minimum total PV curtailments for voltage regulation, with however a very low fairness index. The solution of \mathbb{P}^L over-penalizes the PV owners near the EoF with high curtailments while allowing the PVs near the transformer to operate at their full capability. Therefore, while problem \mathbb{P}^L ensures minimum total PV curtailments, it can create large revenue disparity among the PV owners.

Increasing fairness will lead to an increase in total curtailments and, consequently, to a revenue drop for the PV owners. Relevant works that increase the fairness through penalty terms or by using a quadratic objective function, cannot ensure neither a minimum fairness nor that the increase in total curtailments is within acceptable limits. Figure 2 demonstrates that the increment of fairness in relation to the increment of total curtailments follows a linear relationship for fairness values up to approximately 0.7. For fairness values larger than 0.7, this relationship becomes exponential. Consequently, achieving high values of fairness is not always desirable as it can lead to total curtailments that are multiple times higher than those of problem \mathbb{P}^L .

Note that the point where the trade-off relationship changes from linear to exponential depends on the network topology and on the operating conditions (severity of voltage violations, phase connection and location of PV systems). The proposed CFC scheme therefore ensures that, regardless of the network topology and operating conditions, the fairness of PV curtail-

Fig. 3. Voltage profile at the critical node: (a) no PV curtailment, and (b) proposed CFC scheme with $\alpha = 0.2$.

ments is maximized up to the point of the specified acceptable increment of total curtailments.

B. Performance Evaluation

The performance of the proposed CFC scheme is evaluated and compared with problems \mathbb{P}^L and \mathbb{P}^Q . Note that problem \mathbb{P}^Q is similar to problem \mathbb{P}^L with however a quadratic objective function instead of linear, as given by

$$\mathbb{P}^Q : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_g} (P_{g,m}^C)^2 \\ \text{subject to} & (2) - (4). \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, the CFC scheme is examined with different values of the input parameter $\alpha = [0.2, 0.6, 5]$ for limiting the increase of total curtailments.

In Fig. 3(a), the phase-neutral voltages at the critical node of the LVDG are illustrated when PV curtailments are not applied. Note that the critical node in a radial grid is the node that has the highest distance from the transformer, node 74 in the considered LVDG. In this case, the PV systems near the EoF absorb maximum reactive power based on the Q(V) scheme [6] but its not sufficient. The high R/X ratio of the LVDG and PV inverters that are not significantly oversized lead to inadequate voltage regulation. Fig. 3(b) shows the resulting voltage profile at the critical node when the proposed CFC scheme is applied. While Fig. 3(b) demonstrates the capability of CFC in mitigating over-voltage conditions, similar results are obtained by problems \mathbb{P}^L and \mathbb{P}^Q .

The advantage of the CFC scheme is the controllability that it provides over the trade-off between the increase of fairness and total curtailments. In Table II, the total curtailments and the resulting fairness are given for all approaches for the simulated 8 h. Using \mathbb{P}^L as the benchmark, changing the objective function from linear to quadratic in problem \mathbb{P}^Q increases the fairness from 0.19 to 0.68, with a 35% increase in total curtailments. However, since the fairness increase in \mathbb{P}^Q is achieved passively, there is no controllability to either further increase fairness or to obtain a different solution with a lower increase in total curtailments.

TABLE II
KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

KPI	\mathbb{P}^L	\mathbb{P}^Q	CFC	CFC	CFC
			$\alpha = 0.2$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 5$
Curt. [kWh]	36.2	49.0	42.9	56.8	140.9
Fair. Index	0.19	0.68	0.55	0.89	0.99

Fig. 4. Average power curtailment of all PV systems for different schemes.

In contrast, the proposed scheme is capable of obtaining different solutions based on the preferences of the operator. For instance, the CFC scheme with $\alpha = 0.2$ yields a solution that is guaranteed to increase total curtailments by only 20%, with a resulting fairness of 0.55. In the case that the operator values more the fairness of PV curtailments, by selecting a higher value for α , CFC can further increase fairness. This is demonstrated in Table II for $\alpha = 0.6$ where the resulting fairness from the CFC scheme increases to 0.89. To have fully fair PV curtailments ($f_J = 1$), α is set to a high value ($\alpha \gg 1$). However, as given in Table II, the total curtailments almost quadruple in comparison to \mathbb{P}^L , and are 2.5 times larger compared to the solution with $\alpha = 0.6$ for just a 0.1 fairness gain, from 0.89 to 0.99.

Fig. 4 depicts the average curtailed power of each PV system. It is evident that PV systems near EoF are penalized more under problem \mathbb{P}^L , while those near the transformer operate normally. Out of the 35 PV systems, only nine significantly contribute in voltage regulation, resulting to a very low fairness index. Under problem \mathbb{P}^Q , the curtailment fairness is increased, however there is still a significant disparity between the inverters. In contrast, with the proposed CFC scheme with $\alpha = 0.6$, all PV systems contribute to voltage regulation with low disparity among them. The fully fair PV curtailments resulting from CFC with $\alpha = 5$ are also illustrated in Fig. 4, where all PV systems have a similar contribution to voltage regulation, with however higher total curtailments.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Addressing over-voltage conditions under a growing penetration of PVs in LVDGs is crucial for the network integrity. Utilizing active power control through PV curtailment is an effective approach for voltage regulation due to the high R/X ratio. However, PV curtailments result to revenue losses for PV owners, raising the concern of fairness.

In this work, a novel methodology for increasing the fairness of PV curtailments to mitigate over-voltage conditions in LVDGs has been presented. The Jain's fairness index has been used to quantitatively measure the fairness of PV curtailments and has been reformulated to a SOCP constraint. The proposed CFC scheme explicitly considers the trade-off between increasing fairness and total curtailments. Consequently, the CFC scheme can yield different solutions based on the operator's preferences, i.e., whether to prioritize maximizing fairness at the expense of total curtailments, or to restrict the increase of fairness within a specific limit of total curtailments.

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